

4TH CLASS "MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY" PART 1- 2 THE METHODOLOGY OF ORGANIZING CERTAIN SUBJECTS USING THE "CASE-STUDI" METHOD THROUGH NEW GENERATION TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract. Study of advanced achievements in education, value attitude to education, modeling of the educational process and its implementation in the educational process, effective use of digital technologies in education, development of 21st century skills: 4K is aimed at forming relevant new knowledge, skills, skills and competences for working in cooperation, forming communicative, critical and creative thinking skills and organizing educational activities. At the heart of the research, with special emphasis on highlighting the main story characters and their positive attitude, listening carefully to the child and promoting the views of other group members or the team - the pedagogue's organization of effective and quality education. depends on skill.

Keywords: 21st century skills, elementary school, inquisitiveness, scientific approach, methods, professional development, creative approach, communication, experience, media world, educational standard.

Introduction. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 11, 2022 No. PF-134 "On approval of the national program for the development of school education in 2022-2026", Decree No. PF-5712 of April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030", Resolution No. PQ-4963 of January 25, 2021 "On measures to support scientific research activities in the field of public education and to introduce a continuous professional development system", Tasks defined in the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers dated January 17, 2022 No. 25 "On approval of the Regulation on the procedure for the establishment of a system of continuous professional development of public education employees" and In order to ensure the implementation of the order of the Minister of Public Education No. 121 of April 20, 2022 "On approval of state educational requirements", as well as teachers of general secondary schools to be written based on the content of the priorities set for the introduction of modern principles of personnel policy formation in the general secondary education system by implementing advanced and transparent organizational and legal mechanisms for improving the qualifications of pedagogue personnel based on professional standards focuses on improving the content of continuous professional development processes in primary education based on modern requirements and implies regular improvement of their professional competence.

Order No. 32 of the Minister of Preschool and School Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2024 "On improving the procedure for popularizing the advanced experience and modern methods used by teachers during their work" on the basis of primary school teachers in their work, to study the advanced achievements in education, valuable attitude to

education, modeling the educational process and its implementation in the educational process, effective use of digital technologies in education, development of 21st century skills: 4K - formation of new knowledge, skills, skills and competences related to cooperation, formation of communicative, critical and creative thinking skills and organization of educational activities is being carried out.

In addition, the content of educational subjects presented within the framework of this methodical recommendation is the content, quality, and modern knowledge of the professional activity of elementary school teachers of primary education institutions. provides for their continuous professional development due to increasing the level of knowledge and innovation, effective use of advanced foreign experiences, and wide application of information and communication technologies in the educational process. A pedagogue with the skills of the 21st century, who strives for innovation and is in tune with the times, needs to be a leader in conquering new milestones due to his inquisitive nature and thirst for knowledge. After all, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev said, "The foundation stone of development and the force that makes the country powerful and the nation great is science, education and training." It was emphasized that we should educate the generation as worthy successors of the spirit of our ancestors. Enlightenment scientist Thomas Fawell Buxton said, "Life's experience shows that success is achieved more by diligence than by ability. "A person who works hard for his work will definitely be a winner" - it was noted that any profession owner can work diligently on himself, improving his knowledge and skills.

In conclusion, it is gratifying that our society has large financial resources, capable of accepting and mastering any innovation, new project, new technology that appears in the world. That is why we want the main strategies in the field of education to be based on the development of traditional teaching methods that increase the student's ability to think and provide quality education, along with mastering new technologies.

Research materials and methodology

In the lesson based on the story of the lazy student, the students were divided into 4 groups, and the 4K model skills specific scientific research and classificatory comments were made by the students in the framework of the topic. try to get them interested in the method by trying to get to the heart of the subject. Here, I would like to give a brief classification of the "4K" model: a model that teaches the necessary skills for a student of the 21st century - About 4K: New generation textbooks for elementary school students starting from the new academic year began to study based on One of the main features of the textbooks is that they are developed on the basis of the 4K principle. That is, in this principle, it is not limited to memorizing dry information or simply teaching reading and writing.

Students learn not only science, but also life skills needed in the 21st century. Modern education emphasizes the need to direct students to independent and creative thinking in mother tongue classes. The reform of education is related to the introduction of new innovative methods into the system. One such approach is the "4K" model. The "4K" model, which includes concepts such as collaboration, communication, creative thinking, critical thinking, instead of content focused on memorization, supports the independent activity of the student, forms important skills such as critical, creative and creative thinking, teamwork and is an important factor in improvement. 1) collaboration (cooperation) - formation of the learner's ability to work as a team; 2) communicativeness - development of the ability to communicate with people; 3) creative

thinking - reaching for innovations, making unusual decisions, teaching inventive skills in order to achieve one's goal; 4) critical (critical) thinking means having an independent opinion and expressing it, a critical approach to the issue. This methodology is aimed at the development of children.

These competencies include imagining, presenting ideas, providing evidence, highlighting and searching for missing information, forming one's own ideas and developing the ideas of others, being able to evaluate assumptions and opinions, accepting group goals and evaluating the overall result. They allow schoolchildren to study independently, conduct research with others, and express themselves. If we want to help develop these important competencies, we need to organize the educational process in an interesting and useful way for children. Each lesson at school is a process in which students not only master the content of science, but also gain independent knowledge and develop their abilities independently.

Search results

"Case-study" is an English word ("case" - specific situation, event, "stadi" - to study, analyze) is a method aimed at carrying out teaching based on the study and analysis of specific situations. Try to systematically apply this effectiveness model in your teaching process as follows: In the 1st stage, each small group describes the characters of the story, their characteristics, what time and place it takes place, who or what is the main problem, the behavior of the teacher, mother, grandfather, Dilshad and his classmates, the meaning of his mother. Noli's perspective, kind look, friendly environment, family, school and neighborhood cooperation, the idea of caring for the bereaved or elderly people, the orchard in the school yard and Dilshod's house, an organic garden of events. I paid attention to the fact that the smallest episode, such as the analysis of the creative approach, the diversity of critical opinions, the presence of different views on the events, is fully classified under this small story.

In the 2nd stage, in 4 small groups, the students began to tell their life habits under the influence of the story, in comparison to their elderly neighbors who are in need of help in their neighborhood, and their peers who are home schooled. the care they show, when their classmates are sick, they go to their home or hospital together with the head of the class and their teachers to ask how they are doing, they also remember our values such as kindness between relatives, how emotional their thoughts are clearly and clearly confirming that he is not indifferent to the realities around him and what is going on, which is definitely being discussed in his classmates and family. The fact that he was able to instill a sense of belonging in the hearts of young people, and their excitement did not leave me indifferent, of course. I once again observed that sharing love is a great human virtue, and how much its wisdom and virtue are imprinted in the child's heart, and I am sure that today's children are smart, intelligent and clever! Only, as pedagogues, I should pay attention to the organization of such methods and tactical processes, so that the student can express his opinions and views on the knowledge and skills of each subject in the lesson, first of all, in oral speech, literary have the ability to correctly apply the norms of the language. In order to achieve such an effective result, it is necessary and necessary to remember the requirements of educational standards in every lesson and to follow them from a theoretical and practical point of view.

Teaching the story to the students based on the analysis of the artistic text, in fact, consists in forming a small scientific research project. The essence of the textbooks and methodical guides for teachers created according to the 4K model is based on a comprehensive result, and as a result of interdisciplinary integration, students can create communication, reaction, creative approach,

guesswork, critical thinking, analysis even within a single topic. and is a factor that creates the basis for the formation of the ability to synthesize. Through this only method, through a detailed analytical study of the story, the teacher can listen to the students in a specific context, evaluate the ability to apply grammatical rules in practice, and the culture of oral and written speech. Because we know that the basis of the methodology is an approach focused on the personality of the student.

In the 3rd stage, group members find the explanation and meaning of some words in the text of the story by knowing the meaning of the words and acquire the skill of making a new sentence with their participation. In the next case, based on the title and text, they try to guess the content of the story and tell its meaning. The ability to distinguish the point of development of the content of the story in the algorithmic sequence, when and for what purpose new words are used, the place where the event took place, the space, what the essence of the story looks like, and the ability to guess symbolic explanations. can communicate on After that, gradually trying to strengthen the content of the story through the textbook on the story and, in addition, through questions and answers to the students, requires a little scientific and analytical research from the pedagogue.

As a heuristic conversation, I recommend conducting the conversation verbally so that they can learn, understand and express their views on the event in different ways:

1. What situations did we observe in the story that provide a positive connection to education at school and family?

2. What was the purpose of organizing a picnic in the school garden?

What is the role of the teacher in the formation of positive changes in Dilshad's behavior and actions?

1. Find words that express the character traits of Dilshad's grandfather and mother.

2. What qualities and qualities do you think embody the principle of a "gentle" approach to education?

3. If you were Dilshad's peer, would you act with the same determination as him?

At the heart of the research, with special emphasis on highlighting the main story characters and their positive attitude, listening carefully to the child and promoting the views of other group members or the team - the pedagogue's organization of effective and quality education. depends on skill. The fact that concepts such as affection, friendship, care, family, educational institution and neighborhood cooperation are considered as a special factor even in the first elementary form in a small story requires life experience and high tolerance from the teacher. .

In the 4th stage, the hero of the story shows the positive changes in Dilshad by saying "You can do it!" you can ask the students to express their approximate thoughts in a written speech. Or what other kindness and care can be shown to the elderly, what do you think? during tasks like Of course, such a creative approach was warmly welcomed by the students of the class, and at the end of the lesson, it was recognized as an effective organization. During the story, the final conclusions, the ideas presented as a solution were accepted. The effectiveness of the method is evaluated based on the "Assessment" method, each of the members of the small group is evaluated in accordance with the work performed at the specified time in the training, and transparent recognition by the teacher with analytical feedback on the educational requirements of the competence approaches in answering should be done. I would also like to briefly touch on the dictionary meaning of this method: "Assessment" is derived from the English word "assessment" and means "assessment". If

the activity of each group member, whether their observations are appropriate or inappropriate, is evaluated on the basis of an individual debate with themselves, the formation of the ability to feel free and independent in the child becomes easier, and the mind becomes clearer. The more a child feels free, the more he can develop his thinking ability, self-confidence, and the ability to behave and manage in a team. It is advisable to use pre-prepared incentive cards as an evaluation factor.

Of course, it is very important for the child that the student's attitude, attitude and aspirations do not go unnoticed by the teacher at each stage. Based on the handout presented as a sample, it is appropriate to evaluate all 4 factors individually in a 5-point system. A maximum of 20 points is equivalent to an excellent grade, 15-18 points is a "4" grade, 11-14 points is a "3" grade, and 7-10 points is a "2" grade. Students who have scored up to 7 points are given the following instructions: "Strive more", "Try ", "Search" encourages to gain the desire to acquire new knowledge, and of course, under the supervision of the teacher, special emphasis is placed on forming their interests by giving additional questions and opportunities, which explains the pedagogue's tactical skills.

An example of an assignment by the "Assessment" method

<i>Test.</i> 1. Why was Dilshad ashamed? 2. What are the advantages of teamwork and insects?	<i>A problematic situation.</i> Based on the story, give a specific real-life situation that you have encountered or observed in our classroom or lifestyle.
<i>Symptom.</i> 1. Explain the teacher's behavior. 2. Justify who and why Dilshad's grandfather applauded. 3. Explain how laziness is a vice.	<i>Practical skills.</i> Enrich vocabulary work based on the text, draw your school garden, find Dilshod's positive attitude, count how many characters there are in the story, etc.

On the basis of these criteria, the pedagogue is in his place if he constantly reflects on the development of thinking at the levels of knowledge, understanding, application, analysis, generalization (synthesis), evaluation, in the qualitative organization of each lesson process. it is achieved that the level of students' mastery of the subject is full and the students of the whole class are at a high level. Only in this regard, the teacher should be prepared to plan the level of simplicity or complexity of each lesson in all subjects and develop strategies to positively influence the child's mind and perception. This requires the systematic development of each lesson based on a thorough strategic plan, using a project-based interactive method guaranteed in advance. Only then, when the goal is organized through any form and means of education, it is possible to conclude with 6 factors based on Bloom's taxonomy.

On the basis of the story, the assessment of the groups and the factors of the level of knowledge of the collective knowledge and skills, the state of understanding the content of the story, the ability to apply the educational qualities learned and learned in life, correctly or improves the ability to analyze whether it is a bad quality, behavior or vice. Also, the teacher's attention to embodying the essence of the text in the framework of creative and critical thinking through interaction motivates students to positively express their mastery level. It is important that we emphasize the participation, intelligence, intellect, and scope of thinking of each student in the group when presenting the evaluation system in general. One of the important factors for us

pedagogues is that we try to apply Bloom's taxonomy in every lesson. As we know, the system of questions and tasks - the taxonomy of educational goals based on the levels of cognitive activity, founded by the famous American psychologist and pedagogue Benjamin Bloom, is quite common in the world of modern education. The taxonomy of educational goals should be categorized or systematized by sequentially placing the concrete actions of students, which indicate a certain level of mastery, and the content of objects that become more complex on the basis of natural interdependence. Taxonomy is a theory of classification and systematization of complex structured areas of existence.

As a brief source of the dictionary meaning of this term, the following recognition can be given: Taxonomy (from ancient Greek: *ταξις* - system, order and *νομος* - law) is the doctrine of the principles and practice of classifying and systematizing complex hierarchically related objects. The principles of taxonomy are used in many fields of scientific knowledge to organize the objects of geography, geology, linguistics, ethnography and the entire diversity of the organic world. The main essence of the new generation textbooks that are being created now is the emphasis on the fact that the student can freely observe in the process of communication in oral speech, create a coherent speech with fluent and clear pronunciation, and express the acquired knowledge in written speech without errors in all aspects. It consists of giving. The recognition of the descriptive content of each skill in the 4K model as a separate factor in the formation of this direction depends on the competence of the teacher's scientific approach. Also, always keep in mind the ways of instilling knowledge, skills, competences, attitudes, national values, behavior, as well as modern strategies, teaching methods and methods, as well as the methods of instilling the preliminary preparations carried out by the teacher, to the students.

This automatically creates functions of interdisciplinary integration. From the point of view of quality organization of a single lesson, students begin to feel the incomparable role of science in choosing a profession, giving love to it, and learning a craft from early school age. Homework in the "Essay" method based on a literary text. Here is a brief summary of the Essay method: The dictionary meaning of the word Essay is derived from the French word *essai*, which means attempt, attempt, essay. Students of the 4th grade should be able to compose a text appropriate to their level by purposeful writing in accordance with the requirements of the educational standard of written speech, participate in the process of creating a written text: determine the purpose of the written work, collect the necessary information, make a plan, prepares drafts, collaboratively reviews, proofreads, and corrects errors, and is required to master presentation preparation skills (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.MY.6).

When writing an essay on the topic and presenting ready-made comments in the next lesson, the student should have the ability to set a goal for himself. As a reminder, the teacher should give directions for the exercise of writing skills based on the story discussed in class; teach the stages of the writing process (planning, drafting, proofreading, editing, and presentation); should pay attention to the competence of developing writing skills for various purposes (writing reports, letters, stories, essays, poems and other texts).

Of course, in the next lesson, the teacher should analyze the homework assignment, exchange ideas with each other in oral and written speech, make it possible for them to read their written essays, pay attention to the culture of mutual communication, and express themselves in a monologue. Paying attention to writing skills increases students' love and interest in fiction.

Discussions

Educational standards in the subject "Native language and reading literacy": informational text and graphics suitable for the level of 4th grade in the direction of the comprehension factor, taking into account the requirements of listening comprehension, oral speech, reading, written speech, linguistic competence answers and justifies questions about persons, places, events and facts when the information in (diagram, table, map, etc.) is clearly presented (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.L'Q.A.5); When the information in the text corresponding to the level of the 4th grade is clearly presented, he identifies the main idea of the text or the sentences that carry the meaning and justifies his answer (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.OQ.A.6); People in an informational text suitable for the 4th grade level describe the reasons for their behavior, places, sequence of main events and reasons for their occurrence, problems, solutions and facts, draw conclusions and justify their answers (O'BTD.OTO'S .4. READ.A.8); compares and contrasts two characters, describes the relationship between them; offers a suitable way for the behavior of the heroes (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.OQ.A.9); Determines the topic, purpose and main idea of the informational text suitable for the level of 4th grade, and justifies the answer; determines the author's attitude to the text, paying attention to the tone of the text (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.Reading.A.11); compares the development, place, time, behavior of the characters in the informational text appropriate to the level of the 4th grade with the informational text obtained from the Internet networks, draws conclusions and justifies their opinions (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.OQ.A.15); reacts to the texts taken from the Internet with the printed text corresponding to the level of the 4th grade and justifies his opinions (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.16); Determines the degree to which the content, structure, features and graphic elements of the text obtained from the Internet with a printed text corresponding to the level of 4th grade affect the finding and understanding of information (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.17); online media, advertising, and an artistic and informative text suitable for the 4th grade level, draws a conclusion to determine the audience, the author's point of view, the purpose and essence of the text, and its reliability (O'BTD.OTO'S.4.O'Q.A.18).

After the content of the text is read expressively and figuratively by the teacher through reading comprehension, the given information is based on the idea of the method, and the process of learning continues in an analytical spirit. As a conclusion from the content of the title, the good and bad sides of using the Internet rely on questions and answers after the teacher's speech and the method of reading the chain text of the small group members, and the skills of visual description. The main idea of the informative text "Two results at the same time" is about the effective use of the Internet and the factors within its scope based on the child's age. The fact that the teacher closely connects the content of the text with life events serves to ensure positive results; The ability to find relevant sentences in the text as data 1-3, connect them meaningfully and logically, define new words or phrases creates a basis for small research and research in students.

Pupils develop the ability to easily find the required material from any source, and the ability to distinguish between sentences within the scope of their intelligence. It allows the formation of the ability to search, find, and place information in an algorithmic sequence from a non-textual source, i.e., pictures, diagrams, drawings. It is important to understand what the main idea of these sources is. Because the ability to react to the content of the text represents the regulation of the students' thoughts, so the main goal of this lesson is this. After the text analysis, the tasks of learning the meaning of some words in the informational text, its explanation and synonyms, recording in oral and written speech are performed. The pictures given in the textbook based on this text, the approximate thoughts, the ability to read the text in a low voice, paying

special attention to the use of new words, the development of events, remembering the heroes, etc. we will try" column. Strengthening reading comprehension skills through questions and answers improves the ability of students to independently and freely express their opinions about the text, and to express them through life examples.

Questions and answers can also be submitted as follows:

1. Explain the characters of the text and try to express the activities of each of them in oral speech, to get into the image.
2. Do you agree with Humora and Shakir?
3. What do you understand by the advantages of using Internet networks?
4. What did the computer science teacher like about which student?
5. How would you please your teacher?
6. What do you want to use the Internet for?

We should not forget the possibilities of saying words with a wide vocabulary such as rational use of information and communication sources, media world, concept of media culture, information security, according to the information children have seen or heard. .

Based on the received information, the teacher should evaluate and encourage the students based on the evaluation criteria. As part of the subject, he can give an assignment as required in the textbook or submit an additional assignment as homework.

Conclusion.

Conclusion and conclusion - we conclude the session by concluding on the importance of the development of socio-emotional skills and topics related to learning based on the "Mother language and reading literacy" textbooks. In working with the curriculum textbook, strive to explain the idea that understanding and practicing learning skills can lead to healthy relationships, improved self-esteem, and overall well-being in children. Tip: Don't forget to practice learning skills every day at home and at school in the subjects you teach! Always be sincere in communication with parents and gently explain and explain about their children, first of all, by expressing the positive aspects of their achievements, learning situations and educational characteristics!

Emphasize your involvement as a coordinated task to overcome your student's negative aspects together, relying on a psychological approach! Invite parents to your lessons, so they can see and judge their child's real approach to knowledge and competence!

However, today, every pedagogue, who is in tune with the times, must always be ready to demonstrate his professional ethics and tactical qualities at the level of a high-level culture, sharp knowledge, deep intelligence and perfect spirituality. Because our new generation textbooks require us to improve our relevant modern knowledge, skills, skills and competences in the development of 21st century skills, as well as the 4K model and the organization of educational activities.

Pay attention to the interactive listening comprehension - training steps in the lesson! Its main purpose is to ensure active participation of students in interactive listening comprehension by participating in discussions, guessing, connecting with the text. You can get didactic materials - fiction or informational text, arts and crafts, and review papers. Share and Wrap Up - Allow a few students to share their ideas with the class. Summarize the main points discussed during the session, emphasizing the importance of social awareness and involvement, empathy and inclusion.

In conclusion, the main part of education - be careful to create a friendly environment for children to learn and learn!

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Internet resources:

1. onlinedu.uz is a continuous professional education platform.
2. stesting.uz - testing platform for preparation for international studies.